

The Analysis of Women's Speech in A Movie

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Abstract: This study discussed the areas of women's speech and also the social context that influence the area women's speech. The main character and some supporting characters in the movie entitled "Ever After (A Cinderella Story) spoke the utterances that were analyzed in this study. The topic of discussion was focused on three points. All of the areas of women's speech and the social context that influence their speech had been analyzed and presented by using some linguists' theories in the previous chapter. Based on the preceding analysis and discussion, there were some points to be looked as the findings of the research. There were some areas of women's speech found in the movie. They were: lexical hedge or fillers, intensifier 'so' and 'just', 'empty' adjective, tag question, 'hypercorrect grammar', 'super polite' form, avoidance of strong swear words, emphatic stress, women display greater tendency to ask question, women has greater tendency to make utterance that demand a response, women show a greater tendency to make positive minimal response such as "Mmm, hmm", women are more likely to adopt a strategy of silent protest after they have been interrupted, women use utterance that explicitly acknowledge and respond of the other utterance to the preceding one by talking something related to it, verbosity, question, and also command and directives.

Keywords: Women, speech, movie

I. INTRODUCTION

Human are social beings that live socially. As human live in societies, they need language to interact with other people. Language is the chief means by which human beings express themselves and fulfil their basic needs for interacting with each other. We use language to ask for something and give people information, convey messages or ideas in our daily interaction. We also use it to express our feeling such as admiration, respect, grateful, happiness, etc. Therefore, language is one of the most powerful means that is used in establishing social relationship as well as the important means of communication. The communication can be done using written or spoken language. Spoken language will be used in direct communication. The use of spoken language can be found in our daily life, movie, radio, etc.

In recent year, there has developed an approach to linguistic research that focuses upon language in use within the speech community, which is called as sociolinguistic. Sociolinguistic is interested in explaining why we speak differently in different context, and also concerned with identifying the social functions of language and the ways it is used to convey social meaning (Holmes, 1992:1).

The direct communication of the people in society can be done through spoken language, namely conversation. Through the conversation itself we can see the language characteristics of women. Women tend to be polite and use grammatical form.

Stylistic variation is one of the most interesting aspects of sociolinguistic variation. Stylistic variation itself means that a speaker will speak in different ways in the different social contexts. The speakers who has different age, status, social class, ethnic group, job, etc, will also differ to each other in terms of the speech, this is known as social variation. Sociolinguists are interested in both of stylistic and social variation.

Sociolinguistics also has been defined as the study of language in social context. The study of language in its social context means crucially the study of linguistic variation (Coates, 1986:4). Coates also described the areas

and women's language style, i. e., verbosity, tag questions, questions, command and directives, swearing and taboo language.

The phenomenon of women's speech for me is very interesting to be studied. The obvious examples of the conversation are found in a movie entitled "Ever After (A Cinderella Story)" that contains some sequences of dialogue that were used as the data to be analyzed. In analyzing women's speech, there were some problems appear in this study:

1.2 The Problems of the Study

The phenomenon of women's speech for me is very interesting to be studied. The obvious examples of the conversation are found in a movie entitled "Ever After (A Cinderella Story)" that contains some sequences of dialogue that were used as the data to be analyzed. In analyzing women's speech, there were some problems appear in this study:

1. In what areas of women's speech are found in *Ever After (A Cinderella Story)* movie?
2. What factors that influence the women's speech in *Ever After (A Cinderella Story)* movie?
3. How do those factors influence the areas of women's speech in *Ever After (A Cinderella Story)* movie?

1.3. The Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is mainly divided into two: general objective and specific objective. Each of them will be explaining in the following:

1.3.1 General Objectives

This study aimed generally at increasing our perspective on pragmatics study

1.3.2 Specific Objectives

The aims of this study are related to the problems proposed above. They are:

1. To find out the areas of women's speech in the movie *Ever After (A Cinderella Story)*.
2. To find out the factors that influence the women's speech found in the movie *Ever After (A Cinderella Story)*.
3. To find out how those factors influence the women's speech in *Ever After (A Cinderella Story)* movie

1.4 The Significance of the Study

This study is expected to give positive contribution to the development of sociolinguistics study, as the part of linguistic studies. Moreover, the result of this study is hoped to assist those who need the reference in conducting the same research.

1.5 The Scope of the Study

Related to the problems that have been mentioned above, the scope of discussion in this study is focused on the linguistic features and differences. However, the discussion is limited to:

1. Areas of women's speech as found in the *Ever After (A Cinderella Story)* movie.
2. The factors that influence the women's speech as found in the *Ever After (A Cinderella Story)* movie
3. Areas of women's speech as those are influenced by the relevant factors as found in the *Ever After (A Cinderella Story)* movie.

II. Literature Review, Concepts, And theoretical Framework

2.1 Review of Literature

In this sub chapter some review of articles, theses on literature are presented. Some of papers presented in relation to women's speech. Throughout these pieces of works it is hoped that there would be some information that can be of help for the sake of this research.

Holmes (1992:171-177) claimed that women tend to use standard speech forms because they are status-consciousness than men. The claim is that women are more aware of the fact that the ways they speak signal their social class background or social status in the community. Standard speech forms are generally associated with high social status, and so, according to this explanation, women use more standard speech forms as a way of claiming such status. Holmes also described about women's linguistic behaviour in order to explain the reason of women's politeness and grammatically of women's speech.

Fishman and Hirschman (in Gumperz, 1982:197) described that women have the greater tendency to ask questions, and noted that several of the women-men conversation fell into a question-answer pattern with the women asking the men questions.

Spender (cited in Coates 1986: 103) described about the persistence of this myth of the talkative women by suggesting that we have different expectations of men and women speakers; while men have the right to talk, women are expected to remain silent-talking at any length, then will be perceived as talkativeness in women. The word *chatter*, which is nearly always used of women, has two main semantic components: verbosity and triviality. The idea that women discuss topics, which are essentially trivial, has probably contributed to the myth of women's verbosity, since talk on trivial topics can more easily be labeled 'too much.' The fact that topics such as sport, politics, cars are seen as 'serious' while topics such as child-rearing and personal relationship are labeled 'trivial' is simply a reflection of social values which define what women do as less important.

2.2 Concepts

This study is based on the ideas proposed by some experts in the field of pragmatics studies.

Women and men use different linguistic variation in any community it is claimed that the speakers who have different sex are as one of the factors related to the linguistic variation. According to Peter Trudgill (1984: 88), Linguistic sex varieties arise because language as a social phenomenon is closely related to social attitudes. Men and women are socially different in that society lays down different social roles for them and expect different behavior pattern from them. Language simply reflects this social fact. Men and women's' speech as it has demonstrated is not only different: women speech is also (socially) 'better' than men's speech. Numerous observers have described those women's speech as being different from that of men.

Women's Speech

Jespersion (cited in Coates, 1986: 108) claimed that women have an 'instinctive shrinking from coarse and gross expressions and a preference for refine and (in certain spheres) veiled and indirect expression.' He also states that there are great differences with regard to swearing between different nations; but in those countries and in those circles in which swearing is common it is found much more extensively among men and among women.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

This study analyzed based on the theory proposed by some experts in the field of sociolinguistics study. The following explanation will present the theory in detail.

Hymes(as cited in Wardhaugh 1982: 238-241) claimed a set of concept for describing the context of situation which are considered as the factors that cause the difference on the women's speech. He proposed that the SPEAKING formula is a very necessary reminder that talk is a complex activity, and that any particular bit of talk is actually a piece of 'skilled work'. Hymes used the word SPEAKING as an acronym for the various factors he deems to be relevant. They are: The Setting and Scene (S). Setting refers to the time and place, i.e., the concrete physical circumstances in which speech takes place. Scene refers to the abstract psychological

setting, or the cultural definition of the occasion; Participants (P) include various combinations of speaker-listener. They generally fill certain socially specified roles. A two-person conversation involves a speaker and hearer whose roles change; a 'dressing down' involves a speaker and hearer with no role change; a political speech involves an addressor and addressees (the audience); and a telephone message involves a sender and a receiver. A prayer obviously makes a deity a participant. In a classroom a teacher's question and a student's response involve not just those two as speaker and listener but also the rest of the class as audience, since they too are expected to benefit from the exchange; Ends (E) refers to the conventionally recognized and expected outcomes of an exchange as well as to the personal goals that participants seek to accomplish on particular occasions. A trial in a courtroom has a recognizable social end in view, but the various participants, i.e., the judge, jury, prosecution, defence, accused, and witnesses, have different personal goals. Likewise, a marriage ceremony serves a certain social end, but each of the various participants may have his or her own unique goals in getting marriage or in seeing a particular couple married; Act sequence (A) refers to the actual form and content of what is said: the precise words used, how they are used, and the relationship of what is said to the actual topic at hand; Key (K) refers to the tone, manner, or spirit in which a particular message is conveyed: light-hearted, serious, precise, pedantic, mocking, sarcastic, pompous, and so on. The key may also be marked non-verbally by certain kinds of behaviour, gesture, posture, or even deportment. When there is lack of fit between what a person is actually saying and the key that the person is using, listeners are likely to pay more attention to the key than to the actual content, e.g., to the burlesque of a ritual rather than to the ritual itself; Instrumentalities (I) refers to the choice of channel, e.g., oral, written, or telegraphic, and to the actual forms of speech employed, such as the language, dialect, code, or register that is chosen; Norms of interaction and interpretation (N) refers to the specific behaviour and proprieties that attach to speaking and also to how these may be viewed by someone who does not share them, e.g., loudness, silence, gaze return, and so on; Genre (G) refers to clearly demarcated types of utterances; such things as poem, proverbs, riddles, sermons, prayers, lectures, and editorial. These are all 'marked' in specific ways contrast to causal speech. Of course, in the middle of a prayer, a casual aside would be "marked" too. While particular genres seem more appropriate on certain occasions than on others, e.g., sermons inserted into church services, they can be independent: we can ask someone to stop 'sermonizing'; that is, we can recognize a genre of sermons when an instance of it, or something closely resembling an instance, occurs outside its casual setting.

III. METHOD OF RESEARCH

This chapter describes the research method used in writing this research. The explanation includes data source, method and technique of data collection, and finally method and technique of presenting of data analysis. The method applied in this study is library research, which refers to the findings and collecting some information from various kinds of references that have close relation to this study. The detail is presented in the further discussion.

3.1 Data Source

There are primary data and secondary data that used in this study. According to Booth, Colomb and Williams (2003: 76) primary data is the material that the researcher directly write about "raw data." In field like history and literature that study writers and documents, primary data is the text from the period or by the author that is studied. In such fields, it can be rarely write a research paper without using primary data. Meanwhile, the secondary data is the research reports, whether books or articles, based on primary data or sources. It can be quoted or cited to support the research.

The primary data that used in this study was taken directly from the dialogues on women characters in a Classical English movie entitled "Ever After (A Cinderella Story)." The reason for selecting this movie as the data to be analyzed was because this movie showed conversations in which the areas of women's speech in

terms of linguistic features and styles were found. The secondary data that used in this study were the theories that were proposed by some linguists applied in this study.

3.2 Data Collection

The data of this study was collected through conducting direct observation to the movie. There were two steps in collecting the data. They are:

1. Watching the movie and listen to the conversation of the characters in the movie carefully in order to find out the word's stress, pronunciation, as well as the intonation of women characters' utterances.
2. Reading and note taking the text conversation of the movie in order to find out the sentences, which are considered as women's linguistic features and styles.

3.3 Data Analysis

The collected data was organized in to categories of women's speech and then descriptively analyzed based on the theories applied in this study. There were some steps in analyzing the data:

1. Describing the women's speech in terms of the linguistic features and the linguistic styles.
2. Describing and analyzing the areas of women's speech in terms of linguistic features and linguistic styles as those are influenced by the context of situation.

IV. The Analysis of Women's Speech in "Ever After (A Cinderella Story)" Movie

The utterances chosen are presented as the data in this study. The utterances that were analyzed spoken by the women characters that were taken directly from the "Ever After (a Cinderella story)" movie.

3.1 Analysis and Discussion

There are numerous things to be discussed in accordance with the aims of study within the problems and theories applied in previous chapter. The analysis in this sub-chapter is focused on:

1. The areas of women's speech in term of linguistic features and linguistic styles (which include verbosity, tag questions, questions, command and directives, and also swearing and taboo language) in the movie "Ever After (a Cinderella story)" using the theories proposed by Lakoff (1975) and Holmes (1992), Coates and by Kalcik and Hirshman, Zimmerman and West and Fishman (in Gumperz 1982: 197-201). And supporting theory proposed by Hymes (cited in Wrdhough 1982: 238-241)
2. The context of situation that influence the women's speech which were found in "Ever After (a Cinderella story)" movie using the theory proposed by Hymes (cited in Wardhaugh 1986: 238-240) and Halliday.

3.1.1 The Analysis of the areas of Women's Speech

In this sub-chapter, the areas of women's speech analyzed were based on the linguistic features and the linguistic styles. The linguistic features were analyzed based on the theories that proposed by Lakoff (1975) combined with the theories that proposed by Holmes (1992), Kalcik and Hirshman, Zimmerman and West and Fishman (in Gumperz 1982: 197-201) and the linguistic styles were analyzed based on theories proposed by Coates (1986).

3.1.2 Women's Linguistic Features

The women's utterances analyzed in this study were taken from the utterances of the main character, Danielle, and some supporting characters, such as Barroness Rodmilla (Danielle's stepmother), Marguerite and Jacqueline (Baroness' daughters), Henry's mother, Paullete and Louise.

The women linguistic features found in this movie were lexical hedge or fillers, tag question, Empty adjectives, intensifier 'so' and 'just', hypercorrect grammar, super polite form, avoidance of strong swear words, and emphatic stress.

Lexical Hedges or Fillers

The Lexical Hedge or fillers are performed as in below:

- (1) HENRY : *Am I to understand that you find me arrogant?*
DANIELLE : **Well**, you gave on man back his life but did you even glance at the others?

Analysis:

The utterance in the conversation between Henry and Danielle above, the women character in this case Danielle used hedge *well* in her utterance. It can be seen that she used *well* since she was uncertain about her speech. Danielle judged Henry that he was an arrogant leader and Henry asked her to gave the example about his arrogance action. This situation made her confuse since she could not give the obvious example about it. Beside that in this case Henry was fair; He released a slave who had already bought.

Moreover, the hedge *well* also showed her lack self-confidence of her speech since she knew it was impossible to release all of the slaves and she realized that Henry was fair. Here can be seen that actually she did not know the reason why she judged Henry as an arrogant leader, and she tried to look for the other reason that could support her speech which indicated Henry's arrogance action.

Intensifier "just" and "so"

The intensifier "just and "so" are performed as follows:

- (1) DANIELLE : *Oh, Paulette it feels **just** like Christmas! I get a mother and sisters all in one day*
PAULETTE : *Yes, it's going to be very exciting here, what with the Baroness and all..... Oh, hold still!*

Analysis:

The word "just" in the conversation above was spoken by Danielle. The word "just" in her sentence emphasized her feeling. She felt that the day was like a Christmas since her father married with a widow who had two daughters, so she felt very happy since she would get a mother and sisters in one day, so she felt that it was a gift like in Christmas. And Paulette agreed with what Danielle said.

- (3) DANIELLE : *I hope she likes me*
PAULETTE : *She will love you. **Just** be the little angel. I know is in there somewhere. And do not chew on the bones at dinner and give yourself away. Child your father arrives any moment!*

Analysis:

Paulette (the maidservant of Danielle) spoke the word "just" on the utterance above. The word "just" in her utterance emphasized her suggestion to Danielle that she had to be a nice child and had a good behaviour since she would have dinner with her new stepmother (Baroness Rodmilla) as well as her step sisters (Marguerite and Jacqueline).

In the conversation Paulette suggested Danielle that she had to be polite and not to chew on the bones at the dinner. Here was also seen that the word "just" in Paulette' sentence " just be little angel" had the function in order to emphasized her suggestion to be listened and obeyed by the addressee--- Danielle.

Empty Adjective

The empty adjective are performed as follows:

- (1) DANIELLE : *Perhaps if we brought back Maurice, I would not offend you so.*
Mrs. BARONESS : *It is your manner that offends, Danielle. Throughout these hard times, I have sheltered you and cared you. All that I asked in return is that you help me here without complaint. Is that such an extraordinary request?*

Analysis:

In the conversation between Danielle and Baroness above, In her utterance Baroness used 'empty' adjective *extraordinary*. In the conversation above, Danielle requested Baroness to brought Maurice back. Maurice was one of servants in her house who had been sold by her stepmother—Baroness and when Danielle asked Baroness to bring him back Baroness was really surprised and she seemed to disapprove Danielle's request. Baroness proposed a request back to Danielle. She told that she had sheltered and cared her and for that kindness Danielle had to pay it by helping her without any complaint. So, it was obviously seen that the word *extraordinary* referred to Baroness's request that Danielle had to help her without any complaint. And she asked Danielle whether the request sounded to be amazing to her or could be accepted.

Tag Question

The tag questions are performed as in below:

- (1) HENRY : *And I still can't believe I'm down here while you're up there! And in your undergarments, no less!*
DANIELLE : *I couldn't very well climb up here in that gown, could I?*
HENRY : *You swim alone, clim rocks, rescue servants. Is there anything you don't do?*

Analysis:

According to the grammar point of view a negative tag will follow the affirmative or positive sentence while a positive tag will follow the negative sentence. The to be (is, am, are) and auxiliary (will, have, may, must, can) will be repeated in its tag and verb will be repeated by do, does, or did. According to Lakoff (1975:12), a tag question is used when the speaker is stating a claim, but lacks full confidence in the truth of that claim. Sometimes tag question used in which the speaker knows as well as the addressee what the answer must be, and does not need confirmation. In the conversation between Henry and Danielle above, Danielle used the tag question. It can be seen that the tag question that was used by her showed her lacks full confidence in the truth of her claim. Danielle was successful climbing the rocks before that she slipped off her gown in order to make it easier to be done. Henry stated that he could not believe that she was successful climbing the rocks and up there she only used her undergarments. Then she stated that she could not very well climb up the rocks in that gown. She used tag question *could I* in her utterance. Beside the tag question showed her lack full confidence, here, was also obviously seen that the tag question that was used by her did not need any confirmation since both of the speaker (Danielle) and the Addressee (Henry) knew what the answer must be.

'Hypercorrect' Grammar

The 'Hypercorrect' grammar are performed as in below:

- (1) DANIELLE : *It is not fair sir. You have found my weakness, but I have yet to learn yours*

Analysis:

Remember HAVE + participle means that the activity is extended over a period of time (Sharpe, 1997: 87). According to the grammar point of view the sentence which is underlined above is considered as present perfect tense and the rule is: S+ have/has + VIII. So, the utterance spoken by Danielle above is in correct form Holmes (1992:176) stated that women would simply be using appropriate forms, which accurately reflected their social background. In this case, Danielle's utterance showed her social status in the community. Her status background can prove it. Actually Danielle was from a wealthy family. Her father had a good image and

reputation in the country, but after her mother death her father married with a wicked widow. It was not long after their marriage, her father also passed away. Danielle lived with her stepmother and two stepsisters Danielle was treated harshly, she was treated as a servant in her house by her stepmother (Baroness) and her stepsister (marguerite). Only Jacqueline was kind toward her.

Standard speech reflects social distance. They are used in contexts where people operate primarily in terms of social status and role (Holmes, 1992: 178). Here can be seen that the standard speech form used by Danielle that reflect her social status of the participant—Danielle.

‘Super polite’ form

The ‘super polite’ form are performed as in below:

(1) Mrs. X : *Good day gentlemen. Thank you so much for coming. I suppose you’re wondering why anyone my age would request an audience with the authors of children stories*

A FOLK TALE WRITER : *Your letter was intriguing, madam.*

Analysis:

In the conversation between Mrs. X and the folk tale writer above can be seen that the underlined words spoken by Mrs. X showed her gratitude to the folk tale writers who were coming in order to fulfil her invitation. Mrs. X (the narrator in this movie) wanted to talk about the truth of little cinder girl love story. She wanted to tell about that because after she had read about the version of the Little Cinder Girl. She felt terribly disturbed, and then she wanted to set the record of the story of Little Cinder Girl who was considered as her ancestor.

Women are supposed to particularly say thank you and please (Lakoff, 1975:55). Here, the word *thank you* spoken by Mrs. X indicated her politeness to her guesses.

Women are the experts at euphemism; more positively, women are the repositories to tact and know the right things to say to other people (Lakoff, 1975:55). Mrs. X knew exactly how to behave toward her guesses.

Avoidance of strong swear words

The avoidance of strong swear words are performed as in below:

(1) MARGUERITE : *I asked for our minute eggs, not for one-minute eggs. And where in God’s name is our bread?*

PAULETTE : *It’s just coming out of the oven.*

Analysis:

The utterance that is underlined above was spoken by Marguerite. She used God’s name when she was angry to her servant Paulette, since she had not prepared the bread for Marguerite’s breakfast. At the morning, Marguerite had breakfast with her mother (Baroness) and sister (Jacqueline) and as usually Paulette prepared breakfast for them, but that morning Paulette had not prepared the bread yet because it was still baked in the oven. Marguerite was angry to her and she said, “where in God’s name is our bread?” It can be seen that from Marguerite’s utterance, she tended to avoid of using strong expletive (shit, damn, or one of many other words). But she tended to use the weak expletive – *God’s name*.

According to Lakoff (1997:10) Choice of particle is a function of how strongly one allows oneself to feel about something, so that the strength of an emotion conveyed in a sentence corresponds to the strength of the particle. Here, in Marguerite’s utterance aimed to soften her words. So, in order to fulfil that she used the weak expletive---*God’s name* in her utterance.

Emphatic stress

The avoidance of strong swear words are performed as follows:

(1) Mrs X : *I find your collection of folk tales quite brilliant actually.*

A FOLK TALE WRITER : *Thank you.*

Analysis:

The conversations above were between Mrs. X and the folk tale writer. Mrs. X spoke the utterance, which is underlined above. She used the word brilliant in order to express her judgment. In this case she stressed her praise of the author's folk tale collection by using the word *Brilliant*. Here, can be seen that she praised the author judgment and respected it by giving statement---*Brilliant*, which is, indicated her good impression to collection of folk tales.

3.1.3 Women's Features

In this sub-chapter the women's speech were analyzed based on the areas of features in terms of women display a greater tendency to ask question, women has greater tendency to make utterance that demand a response, Women show a greater tendency to make positive minimal response such as "Mmm, hmm", women are more likely to adopt a strategy of silent protest after they have been interrupted, Women use utterance that explicitly acknowledge and respond of the other utterance and try to link their utterance to the preceding one by talking something related to it and women show a greater tendency to use pronouns "you" and "we", which explicitly acknowledge the existence of the other speaker.

The women's utterances analyzed in this study were taken from the utterances of the main character, Danielle, and some supporting characters, such as BarronessRodmilla (Danielle's stepmother), and Marguerite. The Women features that were found in this movie were:

Women display a greater tendency to ask question

- (1) HENRY : Hello
DANIELLE : What are you doing here?
HENRY : erm..I came to rescue you
DANIELLE : Rescue me? A commoner?
HENRY : Actually, I came to beg your forgiveness I offered you the word and at first test of I betrayed you.

Analysis:

The conversation above was between Danielle and Henry. From the conversation above was obviously seen that women's character Danielle had the greater tendency to ask question. First, when she met him she asked him what he was doing there. Then Danielle asked Henry again whether he really wanted to rescue her after he betrayed and left her since she was only a commoner. And she wanted to know what Henry wanted to do.

According to Fishman and Hirschman (in Gumperz, 1982: 197) noted that several of women-men conversation fell into question-answer pattern with the women asking men questions. Here, the conversation between Danielle and Henry had the same case their conversation felt into question-answer pattern that the woman character (Danielle) asked the man character (Henry) some questions. In the conversation she asked questions for twice to Henry.

Women has greater tendency to make utterance that demand a response

- (1) Mrs. BARONESS : What news of the engagement?
Mr. X : Cancelled. Rumour has it he must find himself a bride before that very night.
Mrs. BARONESS : Well that doesn't give us very much time. I shall need to know who the competition is every move he makes, his agenda and any other tidbits you might pick up
Mr. X : He's playing tennis with the Marquis tomorrow at noon.

Analysis:

The conversation above was between Baroness and her spy (Mr. X), from the conversation above was clearly seen that Baroness's utterance demand a response from Mr.X. The women character in this case Baroness had greater tendency to make utterances that demand responses from the addressee—Mr. X. Baroness utterances

aimed to look information everything about Henry as she said “What news of the engagement?” and “I shall need to know who the competition is, every move he makes, his agenda and every single thing about him.” From both of her speaking turn she demand responses from the addressee. Since Henry was handsome and rich, she wanted him to be her son-in law. She tried to make him felt in love with her daughter Marguerite and by knowing more about Henry whether it was about his agenda, activities or the other thing about him, so she would be easier to do her mission. According to Hirscham (cited in Gumperz, 1982: 197) stated that women’s speech doing more of routine “shitwork” involved in maintaining routine social interaction, doing more to facilitate the flow of conversation. Here, Beside the speaker Baroness demand responses from Mr. X by giving him question about the news of Henry’s engagement. It was also obviously seen that Baroness also tried to maintain the flow of conversation, since she wanted to get more information about every single thing of Henry.

Women show a greater tendency to make positive minimal response as “Mmm, hmm”

(1) HENRY : *Here. Never have you tasted anything so delicious*
(Marguerite opened her mouth and Henry fed the chocolate to her)
MARGUERITE : *Mmm...*

Analysis:

In the conversation between Henry and Marguerite above, Marguerite used positive minimal respond “Mmm” when Henry fed the chocolate to her. She used that response since it was first time tasting a delicious thing like that.

According to Lakoff (cited in Cameron and Kulick 2003:49), women’s communication is expressed nonverbal (by gesture and intonation) than men’s. In the conversation above it can be seen that Marguerite used the intonation of “Mmm” to give her impression of the taste of the chocolate.

Women are more likely to adopt a strategy of silent protest after they have been interrupted

(1) DANIELLE : *Look, Gustave! It’s floating!*
GUSTAVE : *Why are you so happy. You’ll be swimming in manure if they get married.*
DANIELLE : *I don’t know why it bothers you so. I couldn’t careless*
GUSTAVE : *(Interrupted) you’re lying the prince would be your brother in law and you Comtesse de Lancret, would be bringing them breakfast in bed*
DANIELLE : *But they would move into the palace and I could stay with the manor and turn things around*
GUSTAVE : *(interrupted) you like him admit it*
DANIELLE : *.....(keep silent)*

Analysis:

In the conversation between Danielle and Gustave above can be seen that Danielle adopted a strategy of silent protest after Gustave had interrupted her. Gustave interrupted Danielle when she seemed careless about the relationship between her stepsister (Marguerite) and Henry (the man who is loved by her) since she did not admit that she loved Henry. Gustave had interrupted Danielle for twice. First when Danielle seemed to be careless if Henry married with Marguirete, and Danielle did not adopt the strategy of silent for his first interruption by saying “but they would move into the palace.....”. But when Gustave interrupted her for twice by forcing her to admit her feeling, Danielle adopted a strategy of silent protest for that she kept silent and did not answer about that.

According to Zimmerman and West (cited in Gumperz, 1982: 197-198) stated that women are more likely to adopt a strategy of silent protest after they have been interrupted or have received a delayed minimal response. This point was proven when Gusatve interrupted her for twice. Gustave interrupted her utterance by saying you like him, admit it.

3.1.4 Women's Linguistic Style

In this sub-chapter, the areas of women's speech in term of linguistic styles include (verbosity, tag question, questions, commands and directives, and swearing and taboo language) were analyzed based on theory that was proposed by Coates (1986). The linguistic styles that found in this movie were:

Verbosity

The verbosity are performed as in below:

- (1) *DANIELLE* : *A servant is not a thief, sir, and those who are can not help themselves.*
HENRY : *Really? Well, then, by all means enlighten us.*
DANIELLE : *If you suffer your people to be ill-educated and their manners corrupted from infancy then punish them for those crimes to which their first education disposed them, what else is to be concluded, sir, but that you first make thieves and then punish them?*
HENRY : *Well, there you have it release him.*

Analysis:

According to Coates (1986:103), women talked more than men did. In the conversation between Henry and Danielle above this point was obviously seen. Here, the women character in this case Danielle's speech consisted of longer sentences.

Based on society judgment the topics such as sport, politics cars are seen as 'serious' while the society judgment about unimportant or 'trivial' topic, which is chosen by women, is not true in this movie. The topics such as child-rearing and personal relationship are labeled 'trivial' since it is considered as unimportant (Coates 1986: 103). This point was not proven in this movie, since based on the conversation above the woman was also able to speak about economy, and politics and had deep sight about life rather than to speak about child-rearing that was considered as unimportant or 'trivial' topic in society. As we could see form the conversation above, Danielle was able to speak about economy and education.

In order to release the servant she gave reason by stating that a servant or slave was not same as thief. In her utterance She also talked about economy and education factors as her reason why the servant ought to be released.

Question

According to Fishman (cited in Coates, 1986: 105-106), questions as part of the conversational sequencing device of question + answer. In interaction, question are stronger than statements since they give the speaker the power to explicit a response.

The woman to woman questions-answers situation are performed as in below:

- (1) *Mrs. BARONESS* : *You have so much of your father in you, sometimes I can almost see him looking out throughout your eyes.*
DANIELLE : *Really?*
Mrs. BARONESS : *Yes, well... Your features are so masculine. Well,...to be raised by a man. No wonder you're built for hard labor.*
DANIELLE : *Did you love my father?*
Mrs. BARONESS : *Well, I barely knew him*

Analysis:

The participants of woman to woman questions-answers situation in the conversation above were Baroness and Danielle. The topic was about Danielle's feature. Baroness tried to compare Danielle's feature to her father as she said "You have so much of your father in you, sometimes I can almost see him looking out throughout your eyes", then Danielle asked Baroness about the truth of her statement, after Baroness answered her question, she asked her the other question. It was clearly seen that women have tendency to exploit questions. Besides they also wanted to keep conversation going and give the addressee a chance to take part in conversation.

Here, the speaker Danielle had tendency to exploit questions. Beside that she also wanted to keep the conversation going and gave her addressee—Baroness a chance to take part in the conversation.

Commands and Directives

The commands and directives of women are described as in below:

- (1) DANIELLE : Then I won't be recognized. **Hand me that gown** so I can be on my way
- (2) JACQUELINE : I can not breathe as it is
Mrs. BARONESS : If one can not breathe, one can not eat
MARGUERITE : Mother, **focus please!**
- (3) Mrs. FRANCIS : How very kind. Her name?
Mrs. X : Marguerite
Mrs. FRANCIS : Er...Er...Marguerite, we shall have a chat tomorrow, you and I. **Bring your mother.**
- MARGUERITE : As you wish
- (4) DANIELLE : **You will maintain your distance**, sir.
- (5) Mrs. BARONESS : How dare you speak that way. I am a noble blood
Mrs. Y : And you are getting in my nerves! Now **get to work!**
- (6) DANIELLE : **Say it again**
HENRY : I'm sorry
DANIELLE : No. The part where you said my name
- (7) DANIELLE : Marguerite..No! **Put it down!**
MARGUERITE : **Give me the shoes**
- (8) Mrs. BARONESS : Jacqueline. **Go and boil some water!**

Analysis:

According to Lakoff (1975: 18), a request may be equal to the same sense of a polite command because it does not demand obedience but rather suggests something to be done as a favor to the speaker.

Danielle's statement in the example 1 was considered as direct order. The form of her statement was only to ask or order someone to do something, as she wanted. Here, Danielle asked Gustave (her best friend) to take her gown and give it to her, by using the gown she wanted to change her performance in order to make the people sure that she came from a rich family, and could afford to buy a servant.

The example 3, 5, 6, 7, and 8 also showed the same case. In the example 3, was also seen that Mrs. Francis's speech indicated direct order. She was sympathy to Marguerite and asked her to come to her residence in the following day and they would have a chat there. She also asked Marguerite to bring her mother--- Baroness to come. In example 5, Mrs. Y's speech also indicated direct order. She asked Baroness to do her work. In example 6, Danielle's speech indicated direct order, she asked Henry to repeat his speech, when he called her true name. In example 7 Danielle's speech indicated direct order since her addressee was Marguerite (her stepsister), she asked her to put her book down, Marguerite wanted to fire the book and she negotiated with Danielle if she gave her the shoes that she wanted she would give the book back to Danielle.

Meanwhile, in example 2, Marguerite's statement was a simple request. She

Inserted 'please' as the additional expression. It can be seen that form of simple request had the higher degree of politeness. According to Brown (cited in Coates, 1998: 84), that one tends to be more polite to people who are socially superior to oneself, or socially important. Here Marguerite indicated her command to the people who was socially superior in terms of age to her. In the example 2, Marguerite asked her mother to focus on her not to Jacqueline since she needed her mother's favor to choose the best gown for her to be used in Henry's party.

In the example 1,3,5,6, women did not show their politeness to their addressee since it was related to the position and relationship between the speaker and addressee. For instance was in example, Danielle used direct order to Gustave and she wanted Gustave to take her gown. Danielle used the form of direct order since Gustave

had been her best friend since they were children. In the example 3, Henry's mother used direct order to Marguerite since she was much older than Marguerite. In example 5, Mrs. Y used direct order to Baroness since they had equal status as workers in a factory. In example 6 Danielle used direct order to Henry since they had a close relationship, they were a couple. In example 7 could be seen that the conversation was between Danielle and Marguerite, they were stepsisters. Danielle use the direct order to Marguerite and Marguerite did so, they used the direct order to each order since socially they had equal status. While in example 8, Baroness used direct order that is dedicated to Jacqueline, she used the direct order since she dedicated her command to her daughter --- Jacqueline.

V. CONCLUSION

This study discussed the areas of women's speech and also the social context that influence the area women's speech. The main character and some supporting characters in the movie entitled "Ever After (A Cinderella Story) spoke the utterances that were analyzed in this study. The topic of discussion was focused on three points that had been mentioned previous chapter. All of the areas of women's speech and the social context that influence their speech had been analyzed and presented by using some linguists' theories in the previous chapter. Based on the preceding analysis and discussion, there were some points to be looked as the findings of the research.

There were some areas of women's speech found in the movie. They were: lexical hedge or fillers, intensifier 'so' and 'just', 'empty' adjective, tag question, 'hypercorrect grammar', 'super polite' form, avoidance of strong swear words, emphatic stress, women display greater tendency to ask question, women has greater tendency to make utterance that demand a response, women show a greater tendency to make positive minimal response such as "Mmm, hmm", women are more likely to adopt a strategy of silent protest after they have been interrupted, women use utterance that explicitly acknowledge and respond of the other utterance to the preceding one by talking something related to it, verbosity, question, and also command and directives.

There were some factors of the context of situation that influenced the areas of women's speech. In term of lexical hedge, according to Lakoff (1975: 53), they used it since they were uncertain and lack of confidence of their statement. In terms of 'empty' adjective purpose and genre as the factors that influenced the women's speech. In the area of tag question, the topic, genre, purpose and participant influenced the women's speech. In the area of hypercorrect grammar, the genre and participant were as the main factors that influenced the women's speech. The participants and the setting or situation were as the factors that influenced women avoided of using strong swear words. In terms of emphatic stress, the participant and situation were as the factors that influenced the women's speech.

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